

The Deadly Epidemic of Covid-19 in Pakistan and the Socio-economic contribution of Ghazi University during 2020-2021

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Abstract

The educational institutions have been played a central role in the growth of nations and their social evolution especially in emergencies. Therefore, the educational institutions always seem to be the brain of nations and they act as think tanks and are considered to be at the forefront of changing the destiny of the work and they are considered as the center of nation building. If we look at the pages of history, from the invasion of the Tartars to the promiscuity of Al-Azhar University and the horrors of World War II, the veterans of Oxford and Cambridge played their role well during the roar of warships. The role of these institutions in difficult situations was no less than a great achievement. Contrary to the visible aggressor, the modern-day attacker, popularly known as Code-19, secretly broke out in a fit of rage against humanity which is not easy to compete. In these circumstances, the educational and social role of Ghazi University as the inheritor of the centers of learning and the golden tradition, is unforgettable and has been enriched with golden words throughout history. This research paper explores the positive role and contribution of Ghazi University Dera Ghazi Khan which as paid for the construction and development of the nation.

Keywords: Epidemic, Covid-19, Contribution, Ghazi University, Pakistan, Education, etc.

Introduction

At the end of 2019, news of Covid-19 spread from the Chinese city of Wuhan which nothing could be said initially about this pandemic.¹ But in time, the epidemic swept the world, and the economy underwent an autopsy. The covid-19 has hit the economies of developed countries. As a result, the global economic crisis is beginning to arise. In these circumstances,

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Pakistan a poor country is also facing a serious threat of this epidemic. During this perilous epidemic, Ghazi University played it magnificent role with the help of a facility like the first Corona Relief Center in Pakistan, continued to carry out coronary awareness campaigns, vaccinations and, above all, the education process without any interruption under the supervision of Vice Chancellor Professor Dr. Muhammad Tufail. This research article is basically a scholarly discussion on the role of Ghazi University during the two years of Covid-19.

Research Methodology

Primarily this is an analytical study of an institutions located in Dera Ghazi Khan which is considered as backward region of Pakistan. Due to the nature of topic historic method of research has applied through qualitative approach with the help of primary and secondary data i.e. survey and interviews.

Review of Literature

The study of literature is considered to be the central importance in any research. This not only helps to validate the research but also helps to open the door to further research by pointing out shortcomings and gaps in previous research. For this study, consulted the available data not only but also conducted the interviews,

Discussion

This is totally true that the world pandemic covid-19 commonly famous as corona virus has changed the world. Its effects can be felt in almost discipline of life globally. It has also had a profound effect on the education sector. Instead of sitting in the classroom and listening to the teacher's lecture, answering questions directly, the students had to study online. Despite the passage of so many months, educational activities have not been fully restored. Online education continues, albeit in part. No doubt in the human history, education proved a powerful tool of competition among the nations.

Although Ghazi University Dera Ghazi Khan was established in 2014 and has been without a permanent Vice Chancellor for four years. Ghazi University became the largest and best institution of the most backward division of South Punjab. With the launch of new programs in 2019, the university began to take shape. In addition to the development work on the City Campus, developmental work began on the boundary walls of the University's main campus, known as the Airport Campus. Similarly, the redesign of various research projects and agricultural farms has improved many experimental issues. The role of educational institutions in solving social problems can never be overlooked. In this context, the role of newly born Ghazi University in the current situation is significant in Pakistan. If the historical role of Ghazi University is analyzed, then Ghazi University, which was established a few years ago, has played a significant role in this pandemic for the sake of national cause in the current code epidemic and has rendered unique services not only academically but also socially. Also in terms of very large and no less than the old educational institutions. Government of Pakistan formed the first Quarantine Center at Ghazi University.² In this paper, it is attempt to explore the socio-educational contribution of Ghazi University in the following aspects during the hard time of Covid-19 in the world.

Quarantine Center

During this journey of development, the epidemic of Code-19 suddenly declared its existence in the world, it frightening the world. The epicenter was reported from an industrial city Wohan of People Republic of China, however; no tsunami alert was issued, as soon as the world has seen its destruction, the Covid-19 crushed the society and economy of the entire world. Thousands of people were killed in the US and China, while the two countries also accused each other of spreading krona. The World Health Organization called it a dangerous epidemic and advised people to adopt social distance. The west is almost closed. While locked down in China, Wuhan was cut off from the rest of China. These were the circumstances when the world became victim of this terrible epidemic and at the same time the code reached Pakistan.³

These were the circumstances when the world was afraid of the code and in these circumstances it was decided to bring back Pakistanis living abroad, especially in Iran. It was decided to keep about 1600 people brought from Tuftan border in Dera Ghazi Khan. During the outbreak of the epidemic, when 800 people suddenly arrived in Dera Ghazi Khan from Balochistan, keeping in view the national cause, the administration of Ghazi University provided assistance to the government to accommodate the affected and suspicious people in the airport campus. Key and Pakistan's first quarantine center was established on the airport campus of Ghazi University. The sincerity and enthusiasm shown by the top management of Ghazi University, including the Vice Chancellor, in setting up this quarantine center is unparalleled. ⁴ Providing facilities to the victims, Ghazi University handed over its entire campus with excellent assistance. Ensuring water and electricity supply with the help of district administration. Similarly, the girls' hostel adjacent to the city campus was also kept empty in view of the possibility of more people coming.⁵ These services of Ghazi University during the epidemic of Covid-19 were the best effort for the national cause in any way. In the spirit of this national responsibility, Ghazi University helped quarantine about 1,600 people, a large number at the same time. With the provision of campus buildings by Ghazi University in the context of the provision of quarantine center facilities, when these buildings were returned by the district administration, the university received millions in the form of furniture, laboratory equipment and electricity bills. The financial loss of rupee also had to be borne for the sake of national cause. In other words, in the formation of this quarantine center, Ghazi University sacrificed a lot of money.⁶ Thus, Ghazi University was the only educational institution in Pakistan which played a significant role during this epidemic which is the best example of social service along with education and teaching.⁷

Online Education

In March 2020, when the first wave of Covid-19, hit Pakistan, educational institutions closed. As a result of the closure of institutions, the Higher Education Commission directed that when universities thought of moving towards online education, Ghazi University was at the forefront. Ghazi University started online classes through the Learning Management System and MS team and spent a lot of money on licensing the software to provide regular software to its students on a permanent basis. The description of the online system which was the biggest facility offered by any university in Punjab is as follows.⁸

Learning Management System

The world's most dangerous coronary epidemic has paralyzed the education system. At the beginning of the epidemic of covid in Pakistan, when educational institutions were closed, the management of Ghazi University successfully launched a learning management system on the instructions of the Vice Chancellor. For this, a focal person was regularly appointed at the university level, with the help of the IT team, created e-mail accounts for all the teachers and students of the university. Similarly, a teacher focal person was appointed in each department and he provided complete guidance to the students by making these e-mail accounts functional.

Under the Learning Management System, students were added to the e-mail while creating all the classes and the feature of the class also included Student Attendance along with uploading course material and assignments. Every effort was made to guide the students through audio over video lectures. This does not mean that it was a complete substitute for the physical class. But it is better to have something than nothing to say as example was a good attempt. According to HEC, these old and big universities of Punjab were also behind Ghazi in LMS, which is a great achievement and was a success of Ghazi University's struggle to keep the academic activities alive. Therefore, it is a great achievement to continue the educational process without any interruption by creating 8,000 e-mail accounts immediately and the credit for this goes to the Vice Chancellor and the entire faculty who continued to guide his students even in the most dangerous moments of covid-19 in a backward region of Dera Ghazi Khan and adjoining area of Balochistan. The advantage of this struggle was that the students were guided and they were not promoted without examination but the university ensured that at least the knowledge reached their doorstep. Although there may be a lack of effective learning in this method of teaching, the online exam gained popularity among the students, an example of which was the announcement of a regular physical exam by the Vice Chancellor. For all the students who oppose online classes in the absence of a network, online exams were their biggest demand, which the university accepted while compromising on quality. The Vice-Chancellor with full sincerity and hard work took up the responsibility of re-training and rebuilding the nation but the satisfaction of the students was the online examination. Similarly, there was another online mode MS- team with LMS.⁹

MS-Team

Similarly, during this epidemic, from June 2020, software called MS team was also launched for the better education of the students. The University, with the assistance of the Higher Education Commission, regularly bears the cost of several million rupees. This is in stark contrast to the general impression that Ghazi University is charging students fees and teaching online which is free. In fact, Ghazi University bought the license of MS-Team software for the students on their own payment. If anyone buy such software on a trial basis. So for this one has to pay thousands of rupees a month which was not possible for an ordinary poor student. Therefore, Ghazi University has been paying the price of this software continuously since June 2020, while protecting the health of its students. Class on MS team is a very effective, useful and successful experience. It's like a physical class. Teachers and students are in front of each other through a video link. In computer language, the difference

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between them is like hardware and software. Therefore, in my opinion, teaching through MS team cannot be considered as substandard or ineffective and unsuitable. And it is a very effective means of teaching and learning at Ghazi University. The full responsibility and sincerity shown by the university in these difficult times of the epidemic is undeniable, with this now it is also the duty of the students as good citizens have to realize their responsibilities in the same vein.¹⁰

Fee Rebate

Ghazi University, which has less resources as compared to the other well established universities of Punjab, while keeping the semester fees lower than all other universities, did not increase the fees in any way during the code days and showed full commitment to student-oriented and social responsibility. And don't put the burden of expenses on students so that they don't suffer academic loss. Not only that but the Vice Chancellor and the presidents of various departments decided to give more discounts to the students in the fees despite the lower fees from other universities which is a great relief for the poor students of the area. This rebate of fee facility will not only helped the students in reducing their problems but also encouraged them to take interest in education. In addition to the reduction in fees, Ghazi University continues to offer a number of scholarships to its students, including Ehsas, PEAf, Need Base, and Rahmatul-il-Aalameen and large numbers of poor and needy students are benefiting from these scholarships.¹¹

Workshops/Webinars

In addition to teaching matters, various departments are conducting webinars, seminars and workshops with the help of eminent teachers and intellectuals in their respective fields to equip the students with modern academic skills. Will be instrumental in exposing hidden talents.

Ghazi University also guarantees the creative abilities of its students in terms of academic activities. Under the auspices of the Directorate of Student Affairs, several clubs have been formed including Qiraat Club, Naat Club, Debate Club, Writing Club, Art and Culture Club, Clean. And Green, Scouting, Safety Club, Sports Club are more notable. And in this regard, it has introduced its students all over Punjab through numerous programs. So the education and training process is going on with full responsibility and diligence even in the days of code. In addition, motivational lectures in the light of Islamic teachings are the best effort for the mental and moral training of students.¹²

Corona Awareness Campaign

Ghazi University continues to educate its teachers, staff and all students about the dangers of Corona and has set up an SOPs implementation committee. It especially goes to the students in the classes and highlights their social role and their responsibilities in the fight against Corona. Similarly, arrangements were also made for sampling of students' corona test at the university with the knowledge of code and this facility was also provided to the teachers. This is a clear demonstration of high management ability. Seminars on the same first aid have been conducted several times with the help of Rescue 1122.¹³

Development work

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Development work at Ghazi University began and despite the Corona epidemic, the development work that began at Ghazi University continued and the university did not close for a single day. Throughout the epidemic, development work at Ghazi University has been completed. If we look at these development works, they include everything from renovation of buildings to tree planting in university, construction of roads, green lands, landscaping, RO plant, development work in the colony, sewerage system, boundary wall, and filtration plant and the largest parking project are part of a series of development works. Thus, the smart lecture room in every department is nearing completion but the work is nearing completion. While the university is working day and night on e-employment lab, computer labs, digital e-library and many other projects for which the credit goes to the Vice Chancellor and the entire team.¹⁴

Accommodation of Visiting Faculty

Ghazi University appointed visiting faculty to fulfill the requirement of teaching staff in 2019. With the news of Covid-19, lock down situation created in Pakistan by this pandemic which affected badly the employment of the people due to the suspension of economic activities. Various institutions have reduced the number of temporary employees due to financial constraints. But during the epidemic of coronavirus, Ghazi University remained an economic support for the people and did not disturb any temporary employees but continued to provide employment for them which was a wise decision in difficult circumstances. With this decision, while Ghazi University played a role in social welfare, it had to bear a considerable financial burden. However, due to this difficult decision, the stoves of many houses have not been extinguished and of course, it is considered as a good step of the Vice Chancellor of Ghazi University in terms of economic welfare of the society.¹⁵

Conclusion

This is an analytical study that covers the social role of an educational institution during the dangerous epidemic of Covid-19 which can be analyzed in the role of Ghazi University in the solution of educational and social problems in the circumstances of Covid-19. A few points were discussed to make this study easier to examine. Ghazi University, for example, played a key role in the fight against cowardice, as evidenced by the establishment of the Quarantine Center. The first quarantine center in Pakistan, Ghaziabad University, handed over not only its building but also the entire airport campus of Ghazi University and incurred a loss of millions of rupees in terms of electricity and telephone bills. And 1,600 people shifted after being completely cleared

The essence of Ghazi University's role in terms of education and pedagogy is that instead of suspending its educational activities, it continued its online education by spending millions of rupees but also reduced the burden of fees on students. In the same way, Covid-19 was not allowed to become an obstacle in the development works, but the work on development schemes continued throughout the period, due to which today the shape of the university is seen which three years ago was less a university and more a primary school. In summary, the full academic and social role that Ghazi University has played in the days of the global epidemic of Corona since March 2020 is unparalleled in at least two of the nearest regional universities.

Questionnaire regarding the role of Ghazi University Regarding Covid-19

- 1-Covid-19 is a world- wide pandemic.
(A) Strongly Agree (B) Agree (C) Disagree (D) Unknown
- 2-Do you understand Covid-19 is fatal for humanity?
(A) Strongly Agree (B) Agree (C) Disagree (D) Unknown
- 3-Do you think that educational institutions should play a better social role?
(A) Strongly Agree (B) Agree (C) Disagree (D) Unknown
- 4-Do you think Ghazi University has played a positive social role in the days of Covid-19?
(A) Strongly Agree (B) Agree (C) Disagree (D) Unknown
- 5-Provision of Building for quarantine center was great contribution.
(A) Strongly Agree (B) Agree (C) Disagree (D) Unknown
- 6- Do you think it was a good decision for Ghazi University to continue its online education?
(A) Strongly Agree (B) Agree (C) Disagree (D) Unknown
- 7-Do you think LMS is good mode of learning?
(A) Strongly Agree (B) Agree (C) Disagree (D) Unknown
- 8-Do you think Ghazi University tried its best for the betterment of Students during covid-19?
(A) Strongly Agree (B) Agree (C) Disagree (D) Unknown
- 9-Do you think online system of education has proved suitable for Students?
(A) Strongly Agree (B) Agree (C) Disagree (D) Unknown
- 10- Do you think use of technology is mandatory in teaching and learning?
(A) Strongly Agree (B) Agree (C) Disagree (D) Unknown
- 11- Do you thing online education reduced expenses?
(A) Strongly Agree (B) Agree (C) Disagree (D) Unknown
- 12- Online education is not suitable for higher education?
(A) Strongly Agree (B) Agree (C) Disagree (D) Unknown

کورونا وائرس سے بچنے کیلئے سٹاف اور طلباء کیلئے احتیاطی تدابیر!

- ۱۔ لگاتار تھوڑا تھوڑا پانی پیتے رہے اور گلے کو خشک نہ ہونے دیں۔
- ۲۔ سفر کرتے وقت، گھر سے باہر جاتے وقت اور مارکیٹ وغیرہ جاتے وقت ماسک ضرور پہنیں۔
- ۳۔ ہاتھوں کو دھوئے بغیر آنکھوں، ناک اور منہ پر لگانے سے گریز کریں۔
- ۴۔ مریضوں سے زیادہ میل جول سے گریز کریں۔
- ۵۔ پانچ وقت وضو کر کے باقاعدگی سے نماز ادا کریں۔
- ۶۔ بیت الخلاء سے نکلنے کے بعد 20 سیکنڈ تک صابن سے ہاتھ دھوئیں۔
- ۷۔ اگر خدا نخواستہ آپ بیمار ہو جائے تو فوراً ڈاکٹر سے رجوع کریں۔
- ۸۔ بیماری کی حالت میں باہر گھومنے پھرنے سے گریز کریں۔
- ۹۔ ایسی بیماری میں قوت مدافعت کو بڑھانے پر توجہ دیں۔
- ۱۰۔ قوت مدافعت کو بڑھانے کیلئے صحت بخش غذاؤں اور طرز زندگی کو اختیار کریں۔
- ۱۱۔ مصالحہ دار اور بازاری فرائی خوراک سے پرہیز کریں۔
- ۱۲۔ سبزیاں اور پھل زیادہ استعمال کریں۔
- ۱۳۔ پاکیزگی کی زندگی اختیار کریں کیونکہ حدیث مبارکہ میں ہے

(الطَّهُورُ شَطْرُ الْإِيْمَانِ) صفائی آدھا ایمان ہے (جامع الترمذی کتاب الدعوات، باب ۱۰۹، الحدیث ۳۵۳۰، جلد ۲، صفحہ ۳۸۸)

۱۴۔ باقاعدگی سے یہ دعا پڑھتے رہے

اللَّهُمَّ عَافِنِي فِي بَدَنِي، اللَّهُمَّ عَافِنِي فِي سَمْعِي،
اللَّهُمَّ عَافِنِي فِي بَصَرِي، لَا إِلَهَ إِلَّا أَنْتَ

ترجمہ: اے اللہ! میرے بدن میں مجھے عافیت دے، اے اللہ! میرے کانوں میں عافیت دے، اے اللہ! میری آنکھوں میں مجھے عافیت دے، تیرے سوا کوئی معبود نہیں ہے۔

نظامت امور طلباء غازی یونیورسٹی ڈیرہ غازی خان

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